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Agnieszka Bryc, Joanna Piechowiak-Lamparska

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THE ORIGIN OF THE NON-GOVERNMENTAL SECTOR IN RUSSIA DURING THE PRESIDENCIES OF BORIS YELTSIN AND VLADIMIR PUTIN (1991–2008)¹

ABSTRACT

Apart from the public (first) and business (second) sectors, the third sector is one of the pillars constituting the modern democratic society. All the social interests are concentrated within the third sector and they are being implemented by the numerous non-governmental organizations cooperating with the state as well as business world. The birth of the third sector in Russia can be associated with the beginning of Mikhail Gorbachev reforms called the perestroika. The mental changes that the Russian society underwent influenced by the policy of glasnost led to the origin of public involvement into the social and political life, taking upon the role of the often ineffective state. The degree to which the citizens were involved in the activity of the NGOs was first of all associated with their quality of life and it depended on the attitude of the decision-makers towards the idea of social organizations. The time of Boris Yeltsin presidency was characterized by two phenomena: a drop in the standard of living accompanied by the intensification of criminalization within the public life and the positive attitude towards the introduction of the third sector. After the new president assumed the post, the approach of the new authority changed in a negative way and the politics implemented led to gaining full control over public associations. The so-called liberalization of the law in respect to the third sector was only a display of Kremlin's political will and did not signify serious treatment of the principles of the democratic and civic society. The third sector, one of the pillars supporting the civil society is at present in the state of consolidation, dealing with numerous amendments of legal norms. After the period of mimicking western solutions, the Russian NGOs became a power that must be taken into account by the Russian decision-makers.

Key words

non-governmental sector in Russia, third sector, civil society, Boris Yeltsin's presidency, Vladimir Putin's presidency

¹ Translation by Natalia Nieć.

Before conducting a more profound analysis, it is first of all important to think what the “third sector” is all about. The concept of the “third sector,” according to Russian researchers, is strongly related to the idea of civil society. It includes a group of organizations classified as “community,” also called “non-governmental” or “non-commercial – non-profit.” It does not matter what the name of entities constituting the third sector actually is, as without doubt the citizens working within these organizations do it voluntarily, creating active associations. The organizations are non-profit and they do not belong to the government framework.¹ Such a definition of the third sector is presented by the Russian Executive power while they are preparing the basis for the development and activity of the community sector.²

Bearing in mind the concept of the social-economic activity division we need to take a closer look at the first and second sectors as well. The first sector – also called the public sector – consists of state institutions, such as the public administration. It is an area of public activity that includes governing, decision-making and administering on federal as well as local level. The entities of the first sector, supported by legal acts, care for the proper operation of the state and its structures, as well as various other institutions. The second sector, on the other hand, includes the “for profit” activity – such as manufacturing, trade and services. Business that constitutes the commercial sector is guided by economic reasons in its activity (i.e. to maximize the profit and minimize the outlay). It manufactures goods and creates the material basis for the society.³

All three sectors experience mutual interactions – they penetrate one another’s activity and create necessary conditions for one another’s existence. It, de facto, means that the entities of the third sector are not able to function separately from the entire social-political and economic system of the state. Business provides financial means for supporting the non-governmental organizations (taxes), and the public sector ensures the legal as well as organizational activity and thus warrants the legal activity of non-governmental organizations, including tax reliefs.⁴ Due to this special legal status the third sector is able to carry out certain endeavors:

¹ J. Wygnański, *Terminologia* [Terminology] [in:] *Elementarz trzeciego sektora* [A Primer of the Third Sector], A. Gałązka (ed.), Warszawa 2005, p. 11.

² *Портал некоммерческих организаций*, www.portal-nko.ru [access: 27.11. 2012].

³ Z. Lasocik, *Kilka uwag o roli organizacji pozarządowych w państwie demokratycznym* [Some Remarks on the Role of NGOs in a Democratic State], Warszawa 1994, pp. 3–4.

⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 4.

1. If a citizen's participation in influencing the power organs is non-existent, their activity in NGOs allows for exercising civil functions, influencing changes in status quo and taking control (the 1st half of the 1990s);
2. If the community needs are not provided for either by the ineffective government or the market, the NGOs do it in an inexpensive as well as effective way. They then become the symbol of the former two sectors ineffectivity;
3. If there raise community problems, which are difficult to solve, the NGOs lessen the tension and prevent conflicts in the society by assuming the role of the "buffer" or "airbag" between the state and citizens. Through them, the citizens have a possibility to express their views, not necessarily related to "serious politics."⁵

When we think about the functions that can be assumed by the third sector it is important to ask what the factors that provide stability and balance between the state and social organizations are. To answer that question, one can point to three significant factors that strongly influence the development of these relations. At first, the economic and political stability of the country. Secondly, the consistent application of democratic principles in exercising the authority by state ideologists. Thirdly, the standard of political culture and how it is being influenced by individuals and the structure of society. Based on the nature of these factors we will be able to classify the third sector as one of the founding bodies of the modern democratic country.⁶

The debate on the third sector leads to a fundamental ascertainment that "the idea of the civil society (...) was an exceptionally significant element in the attempt to emancipate the society from the structures of real socialism as well as in the process of the system transformation itself."⁷ The notion of the "civil society" did not become the leitmotiv of the social and political transformations at the turn of the 1980s and 90s, however numerous references to "democratization,"

⁵ Ibidem, pp. 5–6.

⁶ N. Belyaeva, *Rozwój organizacji non profit (NPOs) w Rosji. Ich relacje z instytucjami państwowymi* [The Development of Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs) in Russia. Their Relations with State Institutions] [in:] *Pozarządowe organizacje społeczne. Między państwem a społeczeństwem* [Non-Governmental Social Organizations. Between State and Society], S. Golinowska, D. Głogosz (eds.), Warszawa 1999, p. 159.

⁷ P. Frączak, *Spoleczeństwo obywatelskie – transformacja znaczeń* [Civil Society – The Transformation of Meanings], "Rocznik" ["Yearling"] 1995, No. 1 [in:] P. Frączak, *Trzeci sektor w III Rzeczypospolitej. Wybór artykułów 1989–2001* [The Third Sector in the 3rd Republic of Poland. Selection of Articles 1989–2001], Warszawa 2002, p. 29.

“freedom” (of speech, religion, association), “market economy” uttered by the Soviet and Russian decision-makers, did invoke the citizens of the Soviet Union to organize public activity accessible to everyone.

The first non-governmental organizations that were created, mainly participated in the public life by replacing the ineffective state institutions that were not able to provide for the basic needs of citizens. The fundamental purpose of the original community non-governmental organizations (NKO, NPO, NGOs) was a philanthropic endeavor – such as charitable, cultural, scientific, ecologic, sport, and educational activity. The form of the activity was not explicit as well – the majority of organizations that claimed to be non-profit belonged to the genre of: associations, foundations, social cooperatives or small initiatives of private activity. As there was no proper legal basis, the organizations were freely “breeding” solely supported by the growing community involvement.

Some of the civic organizations that previously existed in the Soviet Union were placed under the authority of the state. Contemporary legislation allowed for this form of control over civil activity, as it was laid out in the Resolution of the CEC CPC (Central Executive Committee Council of People’s Commissar’s) dated January 6, 1930: “Regarding principles of creation and elimination of associations and public non-profit unions.” Regulation adopted on July 10, 1932 by the CPC RFSRR “Regarding voluntary associations and unions”⁸ as well as an act, adopted in 1990: “Regarding public associations.”⁹ The time of system transformation in the period of Gorbachev’s authority was different in terms of community activity. Allowing for this sector to develop was concordant to the assumptions of the interior affairs politics, according to which the movement of social initiatives guarded and supported the democracy within the state. The creation of community organizations proved to be an effective mechanism contributing to overcoming public apathy – one of the purposes in announcing the politics of *glasnost*.¹⁰

⁸ *Постановление ВЦИК, СНК РСФСР от 10.07.1932 Об утверждении Положения о добровольных обществах и союзах*, <http://www.alppp.ru/law/konstitucionnyj-stroj/obschestvennye-i-religioznye-obedinenija/7/postanovlenie-vcik-snk-rsfsr-ot-10-07-1932.html> [access: 27. 09.2012].

⁹ *Закон СССР от 09.10.90 N 1708-1 Об общественных объединениях (первая редакция)*, <http://www.law7.ru/base41/d4ru8212.htm> [access: 27.09.2012].

¹⁰ M. Gorbaczow, *Przebudowa i nowe myślenie dla naszego kraju i dla całego świata* [Reconstruction and New Thinking for Our Country and for the Whole World], Warszawa 1989, p. 94.

The change in approach displayed by the Soviet decision-makers towards the newly arising community sector was influenced by factors listed by Marek Rymysza and Annette Zimmer. According to the authors, the evolution of these views followed as the result of:

1. Diminishing state's control over community life;
2. Economic difficulties resulting in the state wanting to use the aptitudes of society and self-help in order to improve the situation;
3. Attempts of the government to control the influx of foreign financial support by legalizing its distribution structure.¹¹

Non-governmental organizations in consequence assumed the role of entities implementing political, economic and social reforms throughout the entire Eastern Bloc, including the Soviet Union.¹² Gorbachev himself made a considerable contribution influencing the change of approach by part of the establishment, as from the very start he did speak about the changes that must take place in the Soviet Union and within its society. He saw the cure for the Soviet Union's ailments only in the complete reorganization of the "top" (the party, state authority organs) as well as the "bottom" (the society).

If we wanted to make a periodical classification of the development in the Russian third sector, we would need to start in 1989, when the first non-governmental organization, the "Memorial" Association was formally founded (although, as we very well know, its activity was actually started in 1987). The stage of assuming the final form lasted until 1992. The following stages were characterized by Tatiana Jarygina and I. Szałganowa in the work published in 1992: "The third sector in Russia" as part of the "Social politics in Russia" series, edited by Grigory Yavlinsky. In the elaboration, the authors pointed out that we can distinguish three stages in the development of the sector:

1. The stage of assuming form that lasted until 1992;
2. The stage of turbulent growth (years 1992–1994)

¹¹ M. Rymysza, A. Zimmer, *Zakorzenie organizacji non profit: relacje między rządem a sektorem non profit* [The Entrenchment of Non-Profit Organizations: The Relationship between Government and the Non-Profit Sector] [in:] *Trzeci sektor dla zaawansowanych. Nowoczesne państwo i organizacje pozarządowe – wybór tekstów* [The Third Sector for Advanced. The Modern State and Non-Governmental Organizations – Choice of Texts], Warszawa 2008, p. 49.

¹² E. Leś, *Organizacje niezależne w Polsce i na świecie* [Independent Organizations in Poland and Around the World] [in:] *Organizacje pozarządowe w społeczeństwie obywatelskim* [Non-Governmental Organizations in Civil Society], M. Załuska, J. Boczoń (eds.), Katowice 1998, p. 135.

3. The stage of final formation (years 1995–1998)
4. The stage of crisis and stagnation (from August 1998).¹³

We can analyze the following stages of development in the third sector in Russia in the light of the law prevailing at that time. Its growth depended and still depends on the political will of decision-makers. However, the crucial factor was and still is the attitude of the Russian society.

In the first period of non-governmental organizations existence the authorities displayed a definitely positive attitude. It was also reflected in the intensified executive process that was to order the legal and financial statuses of the forming public sector. The grounds for the proceedings was the above-mentioned 1930 act of USSR: “Regarding the principles of creation and elimination of associations and public non-profit unions.” Regulation adopted on July 10, 1932 by the CPC RFSRR “Regarding voluntary associations and unions” as well as two decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Soviet Union: “Regarding the procedure of reporting proposals, motions and complaints by the citizens” dated 1968 (it came into effect only in 1980) and “Regarding the procedure of organizing meetings, rallies and street parades” dated 1988. Both decrees regulated the principal laws that governed the activity of community organizations at that time.¹⁴

The USSR Act “Regarding voluntary associations” dated October 9, 1990, influenced by the democratization of the community – political relations, became the foundation for the preliminary regulation of the third sector’s legal and financial situation. Before the act was enacted, all the community organizations were allowed to function as long as they served the development of communism – this ideological criterion was introduced by legal acts passed in 1930 and 1932. However, under the 1990 Act, it included organizations such as: political parties, social movements, trade unions, organizations affiliating women, the disabled, war veterans, children and youth as well as scientific, technical, educational, sport and any other societies that were voluntarily created by their members, with common interests and purpose of action.¹⁵

By affording the term “voluntary association” such a comprehensive meaning the legislative body provided that organizations such as co-operatives, small

¹³ Т. Ярыгина, И.Шалганова, *Третий сектор в России*, “Социальная политика в России” 1999, No. 2, Vol. 37, p. 4.

¹⁴ N. Belyaeva, op.cit., pp. 157–158; *Правовой статус некоммерческих организаций в России. Практическое пособие*, Москва 1996, pp. 7–8.

¹⁵ *Закон СССР от 09.10.90 N 1708-1*, op.cit.

business initiatives or various unions were regarded as non-governmental organizations. As the NGOs were being created in great numbers the authorities of the capital and then other cities began enacting laws detailing the character of “voluntary association,” the legal basis for its founding, functioning, activity and dissolution.

By removing the ideological criterion and simplifying the registration procedure as well as expanding the list of the “accepted” forms of organizations the third sector started a new process of formation based on a new legal basis. This stage of turbulent growth lasted until 1994.

The first steps undertaken for this purpose were taken in the capital city of Russia. It was already occurring in a new reality. The authorities passed a few regulations that structured the status of voluntary associations active in Moscow. By virtue of mayor’s decrees, the city introduced two acts: “Regarding NGOs registration in Moscow” (29 December, 1992) and “Regarding non-profit organizations in Moscow” (30 April, 1993). By taking this step the Moscow magistrate created the legal basis detailing the procedure of founding as well as the principles of activity for organizations, regulating somehow the attributes of “non-profit organizations.”¹⁶ Regulations adopted in Moscow during the process of the third sector organizations formation fulfilled a very significant role. They not only met the acute needs for precision in the non-organization functioning, but also specified the quite general act “Regarding the voluntary associations.”

A decree issued by the RF President “Regarding organization procedures of meetings, gatherings, street manifestations, demonstrations and pickets” had also been issued within the above mentioned period, May 25, 1992. It guaranteed the associations a right to participate in the public life of the state, with a reservation that all of these activities, excluding meetings, must be prior reported to the city hall.¹⁷ The decree regulated the relations between the state and the third sector.

The stage of final formation fell on the period between 1995 and 1998. At this time the legal basis needed for the third sector to operate was already created by the legislative body. The year 1995 proved to have a final say in the affair, as the Civil Code of the Russian Federation became effective. The legislation dedicated

¹⁶ N. Belyaeva, *op.cit.*, pp. 157–158; *Правовой статус некоммерческих организаций в России...*, *op.cit.*, p. 8.

¹⁷ Указ Президента РФ от 25.05.92 N 524 “О порядке организации и проведения митингов, уличных шествий, демонстраций и пикетирования”, <http://www.alppp.ru/law/konstitucionnyj-stroj/prava-svobody-i-objazannosti-cheloveka-i-grazhdanina/2/ukaz-prezidenta-rf-ot-25-05-1992--524.html> [access:11.12.2012].

to voluntary associations included chapter 4, paragraph 5 and items from 116 to 123 in the first part. The Code became the first document that presented the fundamental forms of organizational and legal activity for the non-profit organization and each of the articles had an annotation with information leading to the corresponding federal law. Some of the establishments that were mentioned in the Code were consumer cooperatives, religious and community organizations, foundations, associations, unions and institutions.¹⁸ The RF Civil Code did not, in any means, exhaust the possibilities of activities assumed by NGOs, because there were other forms of action undertaken by organizations that were not taken into account by the legislative body. Federal laws were intended to complement, standardize and specify Russian legislation relating to the third sector issues on the national level. The adopted laws encompassed all the basic legal regulations specifying the following:

1. What the associations are (the principles of founding, registration, activity and liquidation of associations were being specified);
2. Relations between associations and state;
3. Policies guaranteeing non-profit organizations the participation in political life as well as in the decision process.

The above mentioned issues need to be further specified. First, depending on its activity the organizations will adopt a certain form; secondly, the mutual relations between the public and community sectors will change depending on the contemporary interior politics, which will also be one of the factors deciding on its form. Thirdly, the involvement of NGOs in political life and its participation in the decision process. In reference to this problem we will more specifically refer to the three federal laws: “Regarding community associations” dated 14, April, 1995, “Regarding non-commercial organizations” dated 8, December, 1995, and “Regarding charity activity and charity organizations” (11, August, 1995). The principal virtue of these regulations is that they are still valid in its fundamental form and constitute the basis for the entire activity of the third sector.

The first law regulating the situation of the third sector across Russia and becoming at the same time its fundamental act was the federal law “Regarding community associations.”¹⁹ In reference to the structural and legal forms of

¹⁸ *Гражданский кодекс (ГК РФ)*, <http://base.garant.ru/10164072/4/#1004> [access: 11.12.2012].

¹⁹ *Ustawa Federalna Federacji Rosyjskiej o stowarzyszeniach z dnia 19 maja 1995 r. Nr 82-FZ wraz z późniejszymi zmianami z uwzględnieniem postanowienia Sądu Konstytucyjnego* [Federal Law of the Russian Federation of May 19, 1995 No. 82-FZ on Public

organizations that were admitted by the law, the legislative body decided that if on the territory of the Russian Federation and in accordance to the law to associate, the citizens may unite in non-profit organizations that take up the following forms: community organization, social movement, community foundation, community institution, organ of citizen's initiative and political party (chapter 1, art. 7).²⁰

Initially (until 2001) political parties operated on the basis of "voluntary association" law. They were treated as citizen associations established to implement citizen's rights to participate in political life of the state by shaping and expressing their political will. It was to be done by means of participation in community and political actions, elections, referendums as well as representing the citizen's interests in the state authority organs and local self-government organs. However, the above mentioned goals of the party did not place them strictly in the community sector, but somewhere between the first and the third. Due to this problem as well as due to their intense growth, the status of parties operating on the territory of RF needed to be regulated in a separate law. On July 11, 2001 the Federal Law on the political parties was passed.²¹

Subsequently, the act "Regarding non-commercial organizations" dated December 8, 1995 (signed by the president on January 12, 1996), listing the possible forms of non-profit organizations in article 2, includes the following: community and religious organizations (associations), foundations, state corporations, non-commercial partnerships, institutions, autonomic non-commercial organizations, legal entities societies – associations and unions – art. 6–11.²²

Associations with the Amendments and Additions of the Constitutional Court] [in:] *Rosyjskie prawo konstytucyjne. Ustrojowe akty prawne, Tom II: Polityczna organizacja społeczeństwa* [Russian Constitutional Law. Political System Acts, Volume II: The Political Organization of Society], W. Staśkiewicz (ed.), Warszawa 2005, pp. 129–153.

²⁰ Ibidem, p. 132.

²¹ *Federacja Rosyjska. Ustawa Federalna o partiach politycznych z dnia 11 lipca 2001 r. Nr 95-FZ wraz z późniejszymi zmianami z uwzględnieniem orzeczenia Sądu Konstytucyjnego* [The Russian Federation. Federal Law of July 11, 2001 No. 95-FZ on Political Parties with the Amendments and Additions of the Constitutional Court] [in:] *Rosyjskie prawo konstytucyjne...*, op.cit., pp. 93–127.

²² *Ustawa Federalna o organizacjach niekomercyjnych z dnia 12 stycznia 1996 r. Nr 7-FZ wraz z późniejszymi zmianami* [Federal Law of January 12, 1996 No. 7-FZ on Non-Profit Organisations with the Amendments] [in:] *Rosyjskie prawo konstytucyjne...*, op.cit., pp. 169–170.

Another bill that was drawn up in a similar manner was the act “Regarding charity activity and charity organizations” dated August 11, 1995. According to the act, a charity organization included institutions, whose purpose was to provide a broadly defined aid to the needy. It was to be material help as well as support in the domains of culture, education, learning and religion. Institutions that were accepted as charity organizations by the legislative body needed to assume the proper legal and structural forms (associations, foundations, institutions, etc.) that belonged to the group of non-governmental organizations (non-state and non-self-governmental), were non-commercial and created for implementing goals via philanthropic channels.²³ On the basis of such an interpretation religious organizations became a part of the charity activity. Their statutes needed to include postulates relating to this form of community support.

In the “Act regarding associations” as well as in the two other legal acts referred to in this analysis of the third sector in Russia, mechanisms of legal security for community structures were included and described. In fact, it meant that the state supported the newly forming civil society of Russia. From among 54 articles, the attention needs to be drawn to article 17 within which the legislative body clearly specifies the mutual relations between the associations and the state. With a reservation stating that there is a ban on mutual interactions between civil servants representing entities as well as entities themselves with the exclusion of cases mentioned in the Federal Act, it had been specified that the associations can obtain certain forms of support from the state. These include financing the implementation of community programs (state grants), entering into agreements with associations and including all the associations in calls for tender contests on works, as well as services and public procurement contracts within the framework of state programs implementation. Moreover, the principle of common agreement will guide the mutual relations between the associations and the state.²⁴ The approach presented in the act, referring to the mutual lack of intervention in the activity of the state as well as organizations, is compliant with the article 30 from the first part of the RF Constitution. This article guarantees freedom of action for community associations. According to Nina Belyayeva this “*freedom of action* denotes a right to an independent implementation of

²³ Федеральный закон от 11 августа 1995 г. N 135-ФЗ “О благотворительной деятельности и благотворительных организациях” принят Государственной Думой 7 июля 1995 года [in:] Правовой статус некоммерческих организаций в России..., op.cit., pp. 145–147.

²⁴ Ustawa Federalna Federacji Rosyjskiej o stowarzyszeniach..., op.cit., p. 135.

tasks, without external pressure on the activity of the organization, and first of all support of the state in preventing intervention with the internal audit of associations and removal of obstacles in the process of completing the legally appointed tasks (...). This article [no 17 in the act on associations] that includes the ban on intervention into the activity of associations by the state and vice versa guarantees the independence in the implementation of tasks within the range specified by the act, mutual acceptance and respect of the legal status, close observance of the rights and statutory duties of each of them.”²⁵ The rhetoric of the act “On community associations” remained compliant with the approach of the then state authorities towards the community organizations making up the third sector.

On the other hand, the “Act regarding non-commercial organizations” regulates the issues of mutual relations between state authorities and non-profit organizations governed by Article 31 of the Act. According to the law, organs of state power and local self-government bodies are obliged to provide economic support to non-profit organizations in form of partial or total funding of the current management of national and municipal organizations. They can do this in four ways:

1. Granting tax relief, reductions in custom duties and other fees and payments to charities in a non-commercial, educational, cultural and scientific forms in order to protect the health of citizens and the development of physical culture and sports;
2. Granting all types of reliefs to non-profit organizations, including total or partial dismissal of charges for use of state or municipal property;
3. Calling for state and municipal procurements based on tenders (in the non-commercial organizations)
4. Granting tax relief for citizens and legal persons who provide material support to non-profit organizations.²⁶

The legislature sounds similar in the Act of 11 August 1995 “Regarding charity and charitable organizations.” Support for organizations by public authorities and local government was comprised in art. 18 of the fourth section of the Act. The accepted forms of support included logistical and financial support for charities, financial support for the charity programs and providing charitable

²⁵ N. Belyaeva, op.cit., p. 151.

²⁶ *Ustawa Federalna o organizacjach niekomercyjnych...*, op.cit., pp. 169–170.

organizations with a right to benefit from a state or local government property free of charge or on preferential terms.²⁷

If regulations in force at that time are to be treated as a reflection of the principle of mutual accountability relating to the interacting social associations and government authorities, both taking responsibility for the compliance of undertaken activities with the applicable law, it is necessary to observe how the legislature refers to the manifestations of “interference” of the third sector into the “affairs of state.” Mentioned in the laws “Regarding social associations,” “Regarding non-commercial organizations” and “Regarding charity and charitable organizations” the legal and structural forms of the social sector cannot be regarded as a manifestation of interference, but only, as it is guaranteed by the Basic Law, the right of citizens to participate in the administration of the state, both directly (referendums, initiatives and social), as well as indirectly – through their representatives, who represent and defend the interests of citizens, for instance within the framework of operating organizations.²⁸

“The Law regarding Associations” also applies to situations in which the state can have impact on activities of community organizations. It is worth to quote these circumstances as it is very often the case that the regulations included in the act are used by the state for enforcing increased control over the third sector. Article 16 prohibits the implementation and activity of associations characterized by extremist activity, but there is no clear definition of how these extremist activities should be manifested. In Article 38 the legislator established a dual supervision over the third sector organizations by central state institutions. The Prosecutor General’s Office of the RF monitored observance of the law, and the Ministry of Justice were to control that the activities of civil society organizations were in compliance with the statutory objectives (Ministry of Justice supervised this activity in the period from 1991 to 2005, then from 2008 year, and in the period 2005–2008, the organ responsible for registration was a specially appointed body – “Rosreestr” [Registry of NCOs] as the organization responsible for entering the associations into the state registry. Moreover, other supervisory organs of the NGOs were appointed as follows: national financial authorities (controlling the source and legality of income, the amount of generated funds, the payment of taxes), as well as environmental, fire and epidemiological structures. All these restrictions give an impression of

²⁷ *Федеральный закон от 11 августа 1995 г. N 135-ФЗ “О благотворительной деятельности и благотворительных организациях”...*, *op.cit.*, pp. 152–153.

²⁸ N. Belyaeva, *op.cit.*, p. 152.

complete subordination of the third sector, especially in circumstances where direct control would undermine the prestige of the state. Granting authority for supervision of the third sector by state institutions allows them to be entirely penetrated and should a challenging situation arise indicating the ineffectiveness of the state, the organizations are doomed to collapse internally.

At the time of the third sector official formation there were two additional laws established. Together with the three previously cited ones they became the legal foundation for developing a dynamic third sector. The first of these, the Law "Regarding state aid to public associations acting on behalf of children and youth" of 28 June 1995 provided support to NGOs in form of granting tax relief, property tax relief, income tax relief as well as relief from customs taxes. The fact that forms of direct aid to the third sector are at the moment an expression of the government's economic situation may be read in the preamble to the Act of June 28. It says that the term should be understood as measures taken by the RF authorities in accordance with the applicable law, in order to develop and create a legal basis, economic and structural conditions to stimulate the activity of these organizations.²⁹ Only in this single case the form of government aid is explicitly stated.

On December 8, 1995, the second federal law was established "Regarding trade unions, their rights and guaranties of activity" regulating the provisions for citizens' rights to be able to gather in trade unions.³⁰ Thus a legal basis was created for an independent civil activity in the form of non-governmental, non-self-governmental community organizations.

Apart from the purely material assistance to non-governmental organizations the legislator also declared support in form of access to information, staff training and preparation for work in community organizations. It also provided prospects for the following issues: applying for government grants funding programs implemented at the time and concluding various agreements for the

²⁹ *Федеральный Закон "О государственной поддержке молодежных и детских общественных объединений" принят Государственной Думой 26 мая 1995 года*, [in:] *Правовой статус некоммерческих организаций в России...*, op.cit., p. 117.

³⁰ *Ustawa Federalna o związkach zawodowych ich uprawnieniach i gwarancjach działalności z dnia 12 stycznia 1996 r. Nr 10-FZ wraz z późniejszymi zmianami z uwzględnieniem orzeczenia Sądu Konstytucyjnego* [Federal Law of January 12, 1996 No.10-FZ on Trade Unions and Their Rights and Guarantees for Their Activities with the Amendments and Additions of the Constitutional Court] [in:] *Rosyjskie prawo konstytucyjne...*, op.cit., pp. 173–191.

implementation of specific works as well as services and public jobs, including the execution of various elements of government programs and tasks.³¹

One of the turning points during the development of the social sector in Russia was the ratification of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, implemented in 1998 by the Russian Federation. It resulted in the recognition of the jurisdiction of the European Court of Human Rights in RF. Since then, Russian citizens were granted the right to file complaints against the home courts in the European Court for Human Rights in Strasbourg.

The period of Yeltsin's presidency generated strong voices of academics as well as political representatives of various tendencies that emphasized the role of NGOs in the development of a democratic system. However, as there was no standard policy developed for the cooperation with the third sector and there existed a clear legal basis for its existence the authorities did not treat non-governmental sector as a partner. Hence, the leaders of the community sector expressed a distinct lack of trust against both politicians and the state. This issue has been mentioned by Dmitry Nechaev, who points to the aftermath of such an approach. The government assumed only an expectant position, while maintaining a purely declarative support for the nascent civil society.³²

The onset of Vladimir Putin's presidency meant a fundamental change in the functioning of the state. One of the elements consolidating within the Russian system was the third sector, which needed to be adapted to a suitable model of interdependence. The fact that the civil society was a very significant issue for the new president was clear from the beginning of his authority. In the *Message* entitled "What Russia are we building?" delivered to the Federal Assembly on 8 July 2000, Putin said that after establishing the law, it was finally the right time to start enforcing it. He announced a change in economic policy, in which the stable economy will be the main guarantee of a democratic society and will form the basis for building a strong and respected country in the world. This will, of course, only be possible after the society enters into a new "social contract" with the state. A contract based on openness and honesty. The president decided that the most important task was to use the state's instruments to ensure individual

³¹ *Ustawa Federalna Federacji Rosyjskiej o stowarzyszeniach...*, op.cit., p. 135.

³² Д. Нечаев, *Гражданское общество и государство концепции и модели взаимодействия* [in:] *Институт государства и гражданское общество*, Д. Нечаев (ed.), Воронеж 2005, p. 34.

liberty, free enterprise and freedom for the civil society development.³³ And the underdevelopment of democracy was considered to be the root issue triggering all the other problems in Russia. Thus, raised a need to introduce new relations with the civil society. From now on, the concept of “civil society” would frequently appear in speeches delivered by the president, as well as other senior officials, but the frequency of its use would not mean the government approved the third sector’s independence from the state. On the contrary, as shown by experience, the reason of state, which appealed to Putin to such extent, has become the main driver of Russia’s federal authorities. As a result, all areas of citizen’s lives became subordinated to the interests of the state.

The president’s address of 2000 included a doctrine according to which Russia was to become a strong and effective state that will guarantee: 1. stable social development, 2. the inviolability of individual rights and freedoms and 3. economic development of the country. The adopted method of implementation of these tasks was the doctrine of “dictatorship of the law,” which for the third sector meant a radical change on behalf of authorities’ attitude.³⁴ In fact, the result was legislature on NGOs operation of a far more severe character. Changing the leadership team had introduced two consecutive stages. They can, on the one hand, be described on the basis of the applicable law, and on the other, by observing the degree of community involvement in the activity of the third sector. A distinctive feature of Putin’s presidency is therefore a clearly observable reduction in the number of social organizations that operate legally, after having been officially registered. Many successful organizations with quite a plethora of achievements have disappeared from the picture. The new government did not want any organizations appointed bottom-up to be operating without proper – formal or informal – state supervision. The above-mentioned period of activity, which lasted until 2005 can be called the inventory of the third sector, during which liberalization has been replaced by reaction (especially in 2002–2005).³⁵

³³ *Какую Россию мы строим. Выступление В.В. Путина при представлении ежегодного Послания Президента Российской Федерации Федеральному Собранию Российской Федерации 8 июля 2000 года, г. Москва, “Российская Газета”, http://www.rg.ru/anons/arc_2000/0711/1.shtm [access: 27.12.2012].*

³⁴ *Ibidem.*

³⁵ D. Kołbasin, *Trzeci sektor w Polsce. Stan, uwarunkowania prawne, współpraca trójsektorowa. Podstawy prawne funkcjonowania organizacji pozarządowych w Rosji (1989–2009)* [The Third Sector in Poland. State, Legal Conditions, Three-Sector Cooperation. The Legal Basis for the Functioning of Non-Governmental Organizations in Russia (1989–2009)], p. 3.

When new authorities started presiding, new provisions for all organizations to re-register in the Ministry of Justice were introduced. As a result of this process many organizations were denied the NGOs status since their objectives were considered to be a part of the state's domain. An "especially" close attention was paid to organizations, which declared the "protection of human rights" in their statutes. The new regulations had impact on the following societies: Human Rights Centre "Memorial," Glasnost Defense Foundation, The social foundation "Glasnost," the Moscow Centre for the Human Rights Research or the Movement "The Soldiers' Mothers of Russia." The basis for suspending the human rights organizations' activity was given in the legislature, namely the constitutional provision in the art. 2 of the 1993 Basic Law, according to which "the recognition, observation and protection of the human and citizen's rights is the duty of the state." Thus community organizations that dealt with the "human rights protection" were infringing the present law and as a result their activity had been suspended.

Organizations that were denied the right to register were accused of not fulfilling their formal obligations. In many cases, various deficiencies had been identified, based on which it was decided that the organization did not meet the requirements set by the legislature, and therefore had no right to be registered. Some of the most popular shortcomings indicated by the authorities were as follows: meetings of the NGOs collegiate governing bodies were not being held, the protocols were not being prepared, changes of managing body were implemented without proper information sent to the authorities as well as the occurrences of unreported changes in addresses of the NGOs seats and involvement in actions, whose scope was beyond the statutory activity of the organization.³⁶ Taking into account the applicable doctrine of "dictatorship of the law" it could not have come as a surprise that the Ministry of Justice would irrevocably adhere to the letter of the law.

The policy of the third sector inventory was accompanied by the process of state administration decentralization that was also forced by the intensification of problems with public finances. However, this procedure was still occurring within the framework of strengthening the vertical power structure. The government established institutions of the so-called representatives of the President, which were to be responsible for the control of local authorities. On the other hand, they were also accountable for seeking funding from the sources not yet available, which could then be used by the severely indebted country.

³⁶ Ibidem, pp. 3–4.

Due to the fact that the state had been forced to seek new sources of revenue to the budget, the third sector, which was funded by the state, but also by foreign institutions, became one of the sources for obtaining additional financing.

During the years 2000–2005 the federal government's attention has been focused on Russian NGOs also due to mismanagement and misuse of funds allocated to them. Although the examples of corruption within the organizations were rather scarce, it did have an impact on the Russian society's attitude towards non-profit organizations. It was related to the concern with increased crime presence within the community life in the era of Yeltsin's presidency, inducing a feeling of anxiety, lawlessness, chaos and a plummeting sense of security. The publication of scandals involving the NGOs, concerning corruption on the political level, fraud, smuggling alcohol or money laundering, resulted in a decline of confidence towards the social sector. On the other hand, this strategy served the interests of the Kremlin, which was preparing for the so-called "tightening the grip" on the third sector, so its prior discredit in the eyes of the public was very convenient for the authorities.

In 2004, Putin also expressed his opinion on the social sector. In the message delivered on 26 May 2004, the president stressed that there are many effective non-governmental organizations and associations active in Russia. However, some of them do not carry out their tasks properly. Some of them, said the president, were set up solely for the purpose of obtaining financing coming from abroad and others – care only for the welfare of the dubiously originated interest groups instead of acting for the benefit of general public interest. Organizations that included "protection of human rights" in their statutes were classified as these. It seems logical for the head of state to take such measures if we take into account the large involvement of organizations in stark criticism of contemporary politics. Such treatment from the president automatically condemned them to elimination, primarily by cutting off all financial support from the state. They could also be removed from the official register of legal persons under court verdicts as they did not comply with presenting their annual activity report to the registration authority. Before the year 2004, this provision had not been strictly observed, but after the President's proclamation delivered in May, this standard has gained new meaning. The Ministry of Justice announced that if the organization had not provided all the required documents throughout the last two years, this organization did not perform any activity and as such should cease to exist. Moreover, having also lost the appropriate financial support from the independent foundations of the Western world resulted in their dissolution. By expressing such an attitude towards organizations independent

from the Kremlin's influence Putin killed three birds with one stone. First he eliminated the organizations strictly on legal basis, then transferred their money to the ailing state and last created civil institutions functioning strictly under the control of the state. This renewed third sector was to be assisted by political parties created from the broadly defined civil domain. The purpose of their activity was to create a link between the state and society by conducting educational and informational campaigns as well as being present in the local management process and preparing new candidates for the power authorities.³⁷ As a result of the change in approach toward the third sector by state authorities, many organizations needed to re-register and were denied this privilege. Some of the organizations that were not permitted to re-register were the following active human rights organizations: The Center for Protection of Human Rights "Memorial," the Glasnot Defense Foundation, Social Foundation "Glasnost," Moscow Research Center for Human Rights and the Movement "Soldiers' Mothers of Russia," or regional Novgorod Society for Human Rights, Russian Research Center for Human Rights, social organization "Women's Lawyer" from Yekaterinburg.³⁸

The newly adapted policy towards the third sector, which was announced by Putin, was aimed at establishing new relations between the state and organizations, but this time following the rules of Kremlin. On the one hand the state took over some of the associations' tasks and on the other the foreign support was limited and the organizations' activity needed not to surpass the boundaries set by the government. In return the NGOs were offered numerous forms of state support.

In response to the massive criticism of the president and his rule that did not see considerable development in the domain of the civil society concept, on 20–21 November, 2001 Putin arranged a breakthrough event recognized by international environment, namely the Civic Forum. All the social activists that were ready to debate with the authorities were invited to the meeting. Thus the following people sat side by side: Vladimir Putin, Vladislav Surkov, Gleb Pavlovsky and Sergei Markov. The presence of Lyudmila Alexeyeva, the former dissident expelled from the Soviet Union and presently active in the Moscow Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights was to symbolize a willingness of the

³⁷ *Послание Федеральному Собранию Российской Федерации 26 мая 2004 года Москва, Кремль*, http://archive.kremlin.ru/appears/2004/05/26/0003_type63372type6374type82634_71501.shtml [access: 28.12.2012].

³⁸ D. Kolbasin, op.cit., p. 4.

state to cooperate with the third sector. Overall, the meeting was attended by more than five thousand representatives of associations and non-governmental organizations with different legal and structural forms.³⁹ Jakub Benedyczak points out that it was the first time that the president and his entourage openly listened to the accusations of corruption, violation of human rights in Chechnya and restriction of media liberty⁴⁰ Although the declared intention of hosts had been to increase understanding between the state and non-governmental organizations, the liberal activist and Putin's critic Vladimir Ryzhkov claims that it was only another example of the so-called "pseudo-dialogue" "serving the purpose of concealing Kremlin's negligence of democratic principles". For it was quite strictly stated that the government wanted to take control over – so far independent – third sector. The method that the decision-makers wanted to implement in this case was quite popular before and already used in economy. The authorities appointed their potential opponents in various organizations as their representatives. This way they could stay under constant control. The NGOs activists did not want this course of events to occur and refused accepting the implementation of a "central institution to represent them in contacts with Kremlin" as this would mean their consent for being controlled and manipulated.⁴¹

The debate on the "civil society" has always been present in the public discourse. The opposition as well as the ruling party referred to the issue. Although the primary task of the interior affairs was to bring stability to the nation, the authorities could not forget that Russia is being constantly observed by the Western world. Hence Kremlin's decision to appoint their own, controlled social sector. A year after the Civic Forum of 2001 the Committee for the Human Rights was transformed into the President's Council on the Civic Society and Human Rights that was to become a symbol of respect towards society's interests for the Western countries. It was especially valid after September 11, 2001 when Russia announced the war on terrorism and needed to keep up appearances of a truly democratic nation. In 2005 The Civic Chamber of the Russian Federation was created to ensure that Russia wanted "their own model of civil society."⁴²

³⁹ B. Reitschuster, *Władimir Putin. Dokąd prowadzi Rosję?* [Vladimir Putin. Where He Leads Russia?], Warszawa 2005, pp. 142–143.

⁴⁰ K. Benedyczak, op.cit.

⁴¹ B. Reitschuster, op.cit., p. 143.

⁴² The idea quoted after Ludmiła Ledenewa. See: *Czy istnieje w Rosji społeczeństwo obywatelskie?* [Does Civil Society Exist in Russia?], "Socis" 2007, No. 1, p. 58 [cit. per:] V. Dunajeva, *Czy istnieje społeczeństwo obywatelskie we współczesnej Rosji?* [Does Civil

The Civic Chamber was called into being under the Federal Act of April 4.⁴³ According to the letter of the law it is responsible for the interaction of citizens with government and local authorities in order to assist them in their needs and interests as well as protect their rights and freedoms. Its purpose also includes monitoring the observance of the law on the part of the state administration. It is worth to mention here that the idea of the Civic Chambers was initially formulated during Yeltsin's presidency, but it only worked on the local level. The first person to call such an institution into existence was the then Mayor of Moscow Yuri Luzhkov. As a result, in 2008 all the Russian Federation capitals had active Civic Chambers. Was that a sign of a serious approach to upholding democracy by the Russian authorities? Most of the Chamber members were appointed by the president and it was him in fact, who defined the conditions of cooperation and guided the undertaken community initiatives. Thus, this and other projects of the kind indicated something to the contrary – namely the remains of the “Potemkin democracy.”⁴⁴

In the next three years (2005–2008) organizations began the period of waiting for the central government to openly subdue the activity of the third sector. In response to subsequent amendments to the law on the non-governmental organizations activity, Russian NGOs started pursuing an active informational campaign. The purpose of the campaign was to draw public attention to the severely restrictive policy of the state aimed at controlling the third sector. The member of the Interregional Association of Human Rights organization “AGORA” Dmitry Kolbasin points out that the President's Council for the Civic Society led by Ella Pamfilova was especially active in emphasizing the “outlaw” character of the proposed amendments in legislature. The RF Ombudsman Vladimir Lukin adopted an equally critical attitude towards those changes. Under the amended act “Regarding community associations” the following changes were introduced: 1) Establishing a new form of NGOs – branches of foreign organizations; 2) State organs had a right to keep foreign financial support if it threatened constitutional order as well as health and morality of

Society Exist in Contemporary Russia?] [in:] *Federacja Rosyjska w procesie demokratyzacji* [The Russian Federation in the Process of Democratization], J. Tymanowski (ed.), Warszawa 2011, p. 100.

⁴³ Федеральный закон от 04.04.2005 N 32-ФЗ “Об Общественной палате Российской Федерации”, <http://www.oprf.ru/about/1391/law/418/> [access: 28.12.2012].

⁴⁴ B. Reitschuster, op.cit., p. 147.

Russian Federation citizens.⁴⁵ Initially, the government's aim was to introduce general re-registration in order to substantially reduce the number of officially operating associations. However, due to the resolution of the Council of Europe the re-registration provision in the Act had been removed. Lukin as well as Pamfilova saw the regulations as non-transparent and allowing for arbitrary decisions of the officials.⁴⁶ These protests, however, were not really taken into account, as even the president's attitude had not changed until the very end of his second term in office.

The fact that Kremlin's negative attitude to NGOs had not changed was further emphasized by the message of the President to the Federal Assembly delivered on 26 April 2007. In the address, Putin said that "not everyone likes the stable development of our country. There are people who by the use of pseudo-democratic phraseology wish to return to the past: some – to be able to rob a rich nation, plunder the people and the state with impunity, and others – to deprive our country of economic and political independence. There is a growing stream of money from abroad used for direct interference with our internal affairs."⁴⁷ He pointed out that the main beneficiaries of these funds are the environments that use democratic slogans only to satisfy their own interests. Such accusations of the third sector were reflected in a subsequent period, called *Rosrejestracija*.

The Federal Registration Service came into existence in 2006 and was intended to be an organ of detailed control over all social organizations. It monitored the fulfillment of tax obligations to the State, as well as ensured the legality of their business. Dmitry Kolbasin shared interesting insights presented from the viewpoint of oppositionist and representative of the human rights organizations, when he spoke of the so-called period of *Rosrejestracija*. He characterized this period from the perspective of the following regulations: organizations that operated on the basis of previous legislation were denied the right to re-register, the NGOs were recognized as enemies and therefore the fight against them

⁴⁵ Федеральный Закон от 19 мая 1995 г. N 82-ФЗ "О общественных объединениях", С изменениями и дополнениями от 17 мая 1997 г., 19 июля 1998 г., 12, 21 марта, 25 июля 2002 г., 8 декабря 2003 г., 29 июня, 2 ноября 2004 г., 10 января, 2 февраля 2006 г., 23 июля 2008 г., 19 мая, 22 июля 2010 г., 1 июля 2011 г., 20 июля 2012 г., Принят Государственной Думой 14 апреля 1995 года, http://lawcs.ru/index.php?option=com_phocadownload&view=category&id=17&Itemid=33 [access: 28.12.2012].

⁴⁶ D. Kolbasin, op.cit., p. 5.

⁴⁷ Послание Федеральному Собранию Российской Федерации. 26 апреля 2007 года, http://archive.kremlin.ru/appears/2007/04/26/1156_type63372type63374type82634_125339.shtml [access: 28.12.2012].

intensified; the numbers of *Rosrejestracja* employees grew considerably. The period of intense battling the social sector ended with the inauguration of a new President, Dmitry Medvedev.⁴⁸

Certainly, we cannot claim that changes in the office of the president considerably improved the state policy towards non-governmental organizations. All the changes conducted within the state administration structures did not aim at truly reaching out to the public, but only at presenting the new president's image as a liberal to the Western world. The disclosed "dual power" or otherwise called "tandem" – "duumvirate" were intended as purely political games on the line Medvedev-Putin. The "good and bad cop" game presents a classical political construct that had yet to be changed at the time of next re-election to the office of the president.

However, the changes in the image of Russian decision-makers were followed by a new period in the activity of the third sector – it became a part of the "liberal for show" campaign. The process of organization elimination had been stopped as well as the procedure of the third sector's intense control. A year later the three-step program of liberalization was enacted. It included the following amendments:

1. The process of immediate liberalization by removing the priority obstacles related to registration (until July 11, 2009);
2. The liberalization of the tax code (autumn of 2009);
3. Conceptual changes of the NGOs legal situation (until 2010).⁴⁹

Amendments introduced to the Federal Act "Regarding non-commercial organizations" put into force only nine days later, after the first reading, was an evidence of the Russian Federation's transformed policy towards the third sector.

As a result of an over 20 year evolution in mutual relations between the public and community sectors, formulated entirely by political will, the present situation is perceived as dangerous by contemporary decision-makers. The middle class that climbed to their position on the social ladder during the last two presidencies decided to leave the sidelines and become involved. They did not want to be indifferent to the process of change; especially that it also had impact on them. Responding to the question whether the third sector is the foundation of the democratic civil society in Russia, we can say that yes, it is, however it is weak and cannot be compared to traditional civil society. The origin of the

⁴⁸ D. Kolbasin, op.cit., p. 5.

⁴⁹ Ibidem, p. 8.

third sector lied at the foot of changes in mentality that took place within the Russian society as well as within legislature and facilitated the birth of social entrepreneurship. Today, the social sector concentrates on the most significant domains of citizens' lives, replacing the still ineffective operation of the Russian state. Although in the opinion of decision-makers as well as independent observers it does not constitute the main pillar of the civil society, beyond the public and private sectors, it does perform very significant duties indispensable for the functioning of a contemporary state. And Russian politicians have to take this fact into account.